

ЦВЕТА В ЛИРИЧЕСКИХ СТИХАХ Н. ГУМИЛЕВА КАК ОТРАЖЕНИЕ МИРОВОЗЗРЕНИЯ ПОЭТА

COLORS IN N. GUMILEV'S LYRICAL POEMS AS A REFLECTION OF THE POET'S WORLDVIEW

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В статье рассматриваются поэтические тексты Н. Гумилева, содержащие цветовую семантику. Определены цвета, которые автор использует в каждом сборнике, выявлены наиболее частотные названия цветов и преобладающий цвет. Отдельное место отведено цветовой характеристике творчества поэта, дана их общепринятая интерпретация и выясняется, какой смысл вкладывал сам автор в эти названия цветов. В статье приведены сводные таблицы, содержащие данные, полученные в результате анализа девяти поэтических сборников Н. Гумилева. В заключение сделан вывод о том, что автор в основном использует традиционную интерпретацию, укоренившуюся в сознании большинства людей.

The article examines N. Gumilev's poetic texts containing color semantics. The colors that the author uses in each collection are determined, the most frequent color names and the predominant color are revealed. The color characteristic of the poet's work is given a separate place, their generally accepted interpretation is given and it turns out what meaning the author himself put into these color names. The article includes summary tables containing data obtained from the analysis of nine poetry collections by N. Gumilev. In conclusion, it was concluded that the author mainly uses the traditional interpretation embedded in the minds of most people.

Ключевые слова: *цвет, цветообозначение, колористика, цветовая семантика, система ценностей.*

Key words: *color, color naming, colorative, color semantics, value system.*

The relevance of the research topic is due to the fact that N. Gumilev's poetry has not been sufficiently studied: his texts were banned in the USSR until 1968. However, interest in this author is currently increasing. There are many studies devoted to the study of his poetic texts, which also confirms the relevance of the topic of scientific work.

The subject of the study is the colorative vocabulary in N. Gumilev's artistic texts, which is an integral part of the poetic picture of the world, determines the specifics of the artists' worldview.

Research methods: synthesis, generalization, analogy, comparison, methods of literary analysis: biographical, descriptive.

N. Gumilev is considered the most unread poet. A man of encyclopedic education, he absorbed the entire world epoch.

«Gumilev, the poet, is a multifaceted phenomenon, his poetry is complex, like the whole epoch that created it, when much began in Russia and much ended forever. There was a lot of inconsistency in Gumilev, or rather, duality: his tragic dissatisfaction shines through with frivolous mischief, the most tender lyrics and dramatic poems, and even his military prowess, are painted with drawing, sometimes cynicism. And there is always sadness, often unconscious, hidden, through irony, ridicule and bravura boasting, in a major key – a hidden premonition of death» [5, p. 74].

The following stages are highlighted in the poet's lyrics:

- 1) Pre-acmeistic period (collections "The Way of Conquistadors", "Romantic flowers", "Pearls"),
- 2) Acmeism (collections "Alien Sky", "Quiver", "Bonfire", "Porcelain Pavilion", "Tent"),
- 3) The final, culminating stage (collection "Pillar of Fire") [3, p. 2].

Let's look at each of the collections and determine which color names are most frequent in them.

In October, the first collection of N. Gumilev's poems was published – "The Way of Conquistadors", which was published at the expense of parents. The poems were created in his youth. The book was published even before he graduated from the Tsarskoye Selo Gymnasium – when he was 19 years old. The poems in it are immature, not independent. There is a strong influence of the then poetic idol, Balmont (and partly, but to a lesser extent, Bryusov), as well as echoes of various fashionable trends at that time coming to us from the West [7, p. 556]. This is quite a student's book, which the author himself later tried to forget, although he appreciated individual poems.

In this collection, white is most common – 15 times, (airy white, shamefully white, insanely white), red (4) and its shades are often used: scarlet (9), crimson (2). So in the poem Mermaid: "A necklace burns on a mermaid...": rubies are "sinfully red." I must say that in it N. Gumilev writes about Anna Akhmatova (then still Gorenko). In the lyrical work, the beloved is compared to a mermaid. The author uses a complex colorative, which is repeated in the first stanza. The rubies on the necklace are "sinfully red." In addition to the pictorial and expressive function, this color naming performs the function of symbolization. Red here means passion, due to the additional word "sinful" – this meaning is enhanced. The collection contains numerous blue colors (11) and its shade azure (5): the son of a blue height, a blue lily, an azure gaze, about an azure spring. The poems contain gold (8), purple (4), green (2), gray (2): a purple rose, gray, a dead mantle. Black is found only once in the collection, but there is a use of the word "dark" (7): dark depressions, in dark abysses, dark time.

The period 1906-1908, when N. Gumilev was in Paris, is sometimes called by researchers the "dark period" of the poet's life. At this time, he is going through a severe psychological drama associated with personal failures [7, p. 108]. N. Gumilev receives regular refusals from Anna Akhmatova to marry him. Biographers and literary critics unanimously believe that this particular period of Gumilev's life was one of the darkest and most joyless [1, p. 10]. He tried to commit suicide several times.

N. Gumilev has many poems related to death. The first half of life is connected with the fact that it is either a description of death or a desire for death. N. Gumilev is ready to give his life every time. But he did not seek death, he sought life, and even more so, eternal life.

In 1908, N. Gumilev published his second book of poems, Romantic Flowers. The collection published in Paris is dedicated to Anna Andreevna Gorenko. The book includes 32 poems that were previously read by Bryusov. These poems were written in 1903-1907. The Lake Chad cycle stands out among them. Gumilev's first African poems mark the birth of his original talent. In the same collection, the poem "To the Japanese artist Sado-Yakko, whom I saw in Paris" casts a curious re-

flection on the image of a young poet, delighted with the variety of artistic impressions received in the then capital of culture [6, p. 100].

The second collection is also dominated by white (13). So, the author will use it when describing wings, a swan, a lily. It is used not only when describing something beautiful and light. So, in the poem "I dreamed", the author applies this color to coffins: "Two white, white coffins / They are placed next to each other." Red (8) with its shades remains the same frequency, as well as gold (9). N. Gumilev's poems have red frescoes, a red bandage, as well as lips and flames. The color of gold can be found in the description of the ring, sand. In the poem "The Navigator Pausanias ..." there are such lines: "In the golden innocent mountain / The sun went to the sea", in another lyrical work, moisture appears golden: "And the poisoned glitters / Golden moisture of the cup." Blue (5), green (4) are found. Such colors as emerald (3), silver (3), pink (2), crimson (2) appear. Black (9) becomes more, it occurs nine times in the collection. In the author's poems, black panthers flash, curls, beard, and chiton are black. When describing blood, the author resorts not only to the generally accepted red, but also to black: "Red blood will not separate you from the earth, / but for me it is terrible, black."

The color "azure" disappears; as in the previous collection, there is no yellow color.

The third collection of poems, Pearls, was published in 1910. It is marked on it: "Dedicated to my teacher Valery Yakovlevich Bryusov." In the first edition, "Pearls" were divided into four sections, entitled "Black Pearls", "Gray Pearls", "Pink Pearls" and "Romantic Flowers".

In this collection, the color "white" is also in the first place, in addition, it is much more common in this book (21) (white dawn, white earth, white silk). The golden color in the collection can be seen ten times, the frequency of pink color increases significantly (12). So, in "Pearls" pink is the garden, fire, moisture, foam far away. Even Gumilev's paradise is "pink": "A bright paradise that is pinker / Than the pinkest star." There is also red with its shades, and the same colors as: silver (9), green (6), blue (5), blue (4). Examples include the following phrases from various poems in this collection: silver lute, green swells, blue mosses, blue comet. Women's eyes and backwaters are blue: "And the quiet backwaters became / Blue and fragrant."

Brown (2), red (2) appear in the collection, yellow color can be seen once, as well as purple ("purple shadows glide across the meadows"), the emerald color disappears again. It is worth paying attention to the black color (11), which is beginning to appear more and more often. In "Pearls" he has already been found eleven times (black crossbow, on black paths, black blood, black lot, on mourning-black waves, the years are black).

"Acmeists opposed the fragility of symbolic images, declared a specifically sensual perception of the world and fought for a pure and "simple" poetic language. N. Gumilev, creating his poems, sought to use simple, but at the same time bright color meanings that would attract the attention of readers, activate their imagination and imagination. N. Gumilev's color picture of the world helps to immerse oneself in an amazing world filled with exotic, bright colors of the main colors of the spectrum" [3, p. 10].

Thus, the colorative white is the most frequent in the work of N. Gumilev, the author uses it in every collection (Table 1). White color includes all the colors of the spectrum, therefore its generally accepted interpretation may be different. It is a symbol of truth, purity, and luminosity. If we talk about this color in other cultures, then in China, for example, white is an element of funeral ceremonies. N. Gumilev uses white in both general cultural meanings: as a symbol of spirituality, innocence, and as a symbol of death.

The color name gold is in second place in terms of frequency of use. This color is a symbol of divinity, light. Gold is the color of the sun, as well as glory, victory, and wisdom. Researchers note that one of the leading images in the lyrics of this poet is the sun. N. Gumilev is a traveler. The sun can also be compared to the image of a wanderer who makes his way every day. The poet uses the golden color most often when describing Africa.

Table 1. White color in the collections of Nikolai Gumilev

Book	The number of mentions of the colorative
«The Path of the Conquistadors» (1905)	15
«Romantic flowers» (1908)	13
«Pearls» (1910)	21
«A strange sky» (1912)	11
«The Quiver» (1915)	7
«Fire» (1918)	7
«Porcelain Pavilion» (1918)	7
«The Tent» (1921)	9
«The Pillar of Fire» (1921)	4

Table 2. Gold color in the collections of Nikolai Gumilev

Book	The number of mentions of the colorative
«The Path of the Conquistadors» (1905)	8
«Romantic flowers» (1908)	9
«Pearls» (1910)	10
«A strange sky» (1912)	9
«The Quiver» (1915)	12
«Fire» (1918)	3
«Porcelain Pavilion» (1918)	4
«The Tent» (1921)	11
«The Pillar of Fire» (1921)	7

The red colorative ranks third in terms of frequency of use (Table 3). It is the color of fire, blood, power, and danger. Red is perceived differently in different cultures. In Russian culture, this color is more victorious and life-giving than dangerous, as in European culture.

Table 3. The red color in the collections of Nikolai Gumilev

Book	The number of mentions of the colorative
«The Path of the Conquistadors» (1905)	4
«Romantic flowers» (1908)	8
«Pearls» (1910)	7
«A strange sky» (1912)	10
«The Quiver» (1915)	6
«Fire» (1918)	3
«Porcelain Pavilion» (1918)	5
«The Tent» (1921)	10
«The Pillar of Fire» (1921)	10

The perception of red in N. Gumilev's lyrics partly reflects the general cultural perception. The red color in the poet's work often brings negative symbolism, it is associated with sinfulness and corruption. However, during the First World War, the red color ceases to carry this negative meaning and begins to be associated with joy, lightness, and victory.

Black is no less numerous and occupies the fourth place (Table 4). Black symbolizes the absolute, mystery, denial of earthly vanity and splendor, repentance [1, p. 195]. Black is traditionally

associated with darkness, gloom, absorption, and death. This colorative is often used by N. Gumilev in poems about Africa and generally does not carry a negative meaning.

Table 4. Black color in the collections of Nikolai Gumilev

Book	The number of mentions of the colorative
«The Path of the Conquistadors» (1905)	1
«Romantic flowers» (1908)	9
«Pearls» (1910)	11
«A strange sky» (1912)	2
«The Quiver» (1915)	9
«Fire» (1918)	—
«Porcelain Pavilion» (1918)	7
«The Tent» (1921)	12
«The Pillar of Fire» (1921)	9

Green is less common compared to previous colors, but is also more frequent (Table 5). It is the color of life, tranquility, nature, youth, hope. However, in the poet's work, green appears exclusively in a negative way. In Gumilev's poetic texts, this color appears as the color of putrefaction, a painful condition, conveys a feeling of disappointment, decline and decay of the surrounding world. This is due to the fact that green is perceived by the poet as something earthly, which means that it is not perfect, sinful, low. Thus, in the poet's work, this colorative is mainly used in a negative way.

Table 5. The green color in the collections of Nikolai Gumilev

Book	The number of mentions of the colorative
«The Path of the Conquistadors» (1905)	2
«Romantic flowers» (1908)	4
«Pearls» (1910)	6
«A strange sky» (1912)	4
«The Quiver» (1915)	8
«Fire» (1918)	4
«Porcelain Pavilion» (1918)	—
«The Tent» (1921)	11
«The Pillar of Fire» (1921)	2

In general, it can be said that N. Gumilev uses simple frequency color names, which have a mostly traditional interpretation embedded in the minds of most people.

N. Gumilev traveled a lot and sought to incorporate into his poetry all the richness and beauty of the surrounding world. This largely determined the romantic nature of his artistic texts, characterized by a harmonious combination of visual and expressive means, sophistication of rhymes, clarity and accuracy of poetic realities.

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